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ASSESSMENT OF A LOW TEMPERATURE CURE RESIN HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPOSITE OVERWRAP REPAIR

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Introduction

- In principle, this involves building up layers of laminate over the defect area until the original design pressure of the pipe is restored.
- Fabric and resin are brought together onsite just prior to wrapping using a portable prepregger; favourable in terms of material and quality management
- Generally used for repair of wall-thinning (pressure containment) and through-wall (leak containment) defects.
- Versatile (varying profiles, tight space)
- Arrest external corrosion

Low Temperature Cure Resin for High Temperature Application

This study is to investigate the **long term thermal stability** and **degradation behaviour** of a **low temperature cure resin** for potential use as composite overwrap repairs in temperatures between **160°C and 250°C**.

- Note that, in this study, for an assumed **6-month** period to end of life and maximum of **14% resin weight loss*** is set as end of life criteria, a maximum resin weight loss rate of **0.079% day⁻¹** is allowed.
- **Lab tests** carried out using ovens in laboratory at **200°C** and **250°C**.
- **Field tests** carried out on actual elevated temperature piping operated in a petrochemical plant at **160°C, 200°C** and **250°C**.
- **Thermal degradation** of both tests were monitored via:
 - **Visual observation,**
 - Rate of **weight change** measurements and
 - Chemical change using **FTIR analysis**

* Based on previous work, loss of adhesion starts when resin weight loss is 14% which approximately 5% of total weight

Lab Test Specimen Preparation

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- Resin were cast into bars in slotted aluminium blocks with slot dimension of 20 x 30 x 60 mm.
- Resin specimens were cured in the slotted aluminium block at 100°C for 16 hours, followed by postcuring at two separate temperatures: 200°C or 250°C for 3 hours.
- 10 samples were made for each postcure temperature.
- The postcuring procedure is to eliminate any weight loss due to effect of uncured resin

Lab test specimen in a tray after 600 hours exposure at 250°C in laboratory oven

Field Test Specimen Preparation ... 1/2

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8 layers on
19 mm pipe

Cured at
100°C for
16 hours in
oven

Postcuring at
three separate
temperatures:
160°C, 200°C
or 250°C for 3
hours in oven

Cut to 50 mm length
and quarter of the
circumference

TGA results worked out
the average resin weight
content at 35 wt%

Normalise
weight loss

Tests

- TGA – resin weight fraction
- DSC – Degree of cure

Offcut

Field Test Specimen Preparation ... 2/2

Steam trap line operated
at 160°C

Steam trap line operated
at 200°C

Steam trap line operated
at 250°C

- Eight specimen (four specimen to form one complete tubular composite) were wire tied on each 19 mm piping
- Monitoring activity was carried out periodically to assess the stability of the composites over time

At 250°C, after 600

hours
Darker colour &
Weight loss

At 250°C, after 1,000

hours

Lab Test pass the maximum allowable resin weight loss rate of 0.083% day⁻¹. Hence, proceed the study to field test

Lab Test Results

Resin weight loss rate:
250°C (lab) = 0.069 % day⁻¹
200°C (lab) = 0.014 % day⁻¹

Field Test Results ... 1/2

Specimens on pipe at site exposed at 200°C, after various exposure times

1,000 hrs

2,000 hrs

3,000 hrs

4,300 hrs

Specimens collected from site that was exposed at 250°C, after various exposure times

Darker colour & weight loss

Challenge: Unavoidable temperature fluctuations

Field Test Results ... 2/2

- Higher exposure temperature lead to higher degradation rate.
- Only 160°C field test specimen pass the maximum allowable resin weight loss rate of 0.079% day⁻¹.

FTIR results

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Lab test

Field test

- Diminution/loss of peaks at 1360 cm^{-1} (green box) and 810 ~ 820 cm^{-1} (red box) spectra region of aged specimen, show decomposed of triazine and aromatic ring of polycyanurate

Summary and Conclusion

- Specimen was characterized to determine rate of degradation under continuous thermal exposure by visual observation, weight loss monitoring and chemical change confirmed by FTIR analysis.
- Higher exposure temperature lead to higher degradation rate.
- Field test specimen were subjected to actual operating thermal and environmental exposure.
- Degradation rate of field test specimen was found to be more severe than lab test conditioned specimen.
- Likely due to the more severe exposure conditions (i.e. fluctuating temperatures, moisture and radiation) found in plant environment as compared laboratory aged specimen.
- In field test, only 160°C specimen pass the maximum allowable resin weight loss rate of 0.079% day⁻¹ (maximum 15% resin weight loss in 6 months).
- Therefore, this formulation could only work up to 160°C as temporary repair up to 6 months in field environment.

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THANK YOU!

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